

Visible light activity of sulfur doped TiO₂ nanoparticles prepared by one step process

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The present research work emphasizes a new approach to prepare sulfur doped TiO₂ nanoparticles by one step chemical process. The main intent of this work is to reduce the demerits of sulfur (S) doped TiO₂ nanoparticles preparation, in requisites of the simple, cost effective, and mass preparation parameters. The physicochemical properties of undoped and doped TiO₂ were emphasized by XRD, FTIR, UV-Vis, PL, SEM with EDS and TEM analysis. The observed results shows the smaller crystallite size (10–12 nm) with spherical morphology of individual grains based on the XRD, SEM and TEM analysis results. From the UV-Visible and PL analyses, it observed that the S doped TiO₂ has been improved the UV and Visible absorption. The optimized results were exhibits sulfur doping escalating the photogenerated electrons and holes during the photocatalytic reaction. The obtained nanoparticles can be utilized in photovoltaic devices as photoanode material.

Keywords: Sulfur doped TiO₂, visible light active, single step process, photocatalytic.

Introduction

Titanium dioxide, also known as titanium(IV) oxide or titania (TiO₂), is a naturally occurring ninth most abundant oxide of titanium component. Since, this research work was commercial initiative in the early twentieth century. The structure of rutile and anatase can be described as tetragonal while brookite structure is depicted as orthorhombic¹. Different synthesis methods are explored and developed for the preparation of TiO₂ nanoparticles including sol-gel², sonication³, hydrothermal⁴, ball mill⁵ and spray pyrolysis⁶.

Recent years a surge of invest in tuning the optical properties of TiO₂ nanoparticles for wide range of applications. The doping of sulfur in TiO₂ materials can enhance the absorption towards the visible spectrum during the photocatalytic activity. While analyzing this concept, we found that the surface modification of TiO₂ under visible light is significant. The chemical composition of TiO₂ can be changed by doping of metal (Fe, Ce, Cu, Zr, V, Mo etc.) and non-metal (C, N, S, F, B etc.)^{7,8} components enhance optical as well as catalytic properties. It is require tremendous usage of material in energy crises via solar energy based on photovoltaic, water splitting, hydrogen preparation, and storage devices⁹.

The non-metal ions doping with TiO₂ reduces the band

gap value and form density of states. The sulfur doped TiO₂ (S-TiO₂) can be achieved through processes such as sol-gel, solvothermal, high temperature reactions, and hydrothermal¹⁰. The main aim of this work is to reduce the demerits of S-TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesis via simple, cost effective, and mass preparation parameters. The different characterisation techniques are used to analyze the effect of sulfur alteration in TiO₂ nanoparticles.

Experimental

Chemical reagents sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄: 98%, Merck) and titanium(IV) isopropoxide (Ti(OCH(CH₃)₂)₄): 99%, Merck) were purchased and used for the preparation of nanoparticles without any additional purification. The double distilled (DD) water was also used for the process of preparation. In this preparation method 7 M of H₂SO₄ (120 mL) was placed in a beaker. In this solution, 30 mL of titanium isopropoxide [Ti(OPr)₄] was added (drop wise) under magnetic stirring for 3 h. After the mixture was aged overnight to obtain the gel, it was then dried at 353 K for about 12 h in a hot air oven. The final S doped TiO₂ nanoparticles were obtained once the mixture was ground to a fine powder, and then calcined at 673 K for 3 h in a muffle furnace under air atmosphere at a heating rate of 278 K per minute. The un-doped TiO₂

nanoparticles were synthesized using the same chemical precursor and procedure barring the use of 120 mL of DD water instead of H₂SO₄ solution.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern of the samples S-doped and pure TiO₂ nanoparticles. The absorbed XRD patterns for two samples are compared with the JCPDS (JCPDS card: 21-1272, 1999) and it coordinated well with the reported phase of anatase TiO₂, which indicate a crystalline nature with mainly anatase structure of samples. It shows a major peaks A (101), A (004), A (200), A (105), A (204), A (220), and A (215) dominated in two samples. The other phases of TiO₂ possess a lower electron transport capability than the anatase phase of TiO₂, which is responsible for higher photovoltaic performance¹¹. The average crystalline dimension along with the crystal plane (101) at 2θ = 25.5° has been approximated from the full width half maximum of the diffraction peaks using Scherer equation for (101) plane¹¹, by analyzing the results of XRD pattern. The average crystallite sizes are found to be 10 nm and 12 nm for S-doped and pure TiO₂ samples respectively.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of prepared S doped and pure TiO₂ nanoparticles.

The FTIR spectral assignments of the sample are shown in Fig. 2. The stretching vibration of Ti-O-Ti and Ti-O bonds is liable for the broad strong and similar peaks for two samples the range between 400 and 700 cm⁻¹. It exhibits the existence of TiO₂ molecules in the sample^{12,13}. When undoped TiO₂ sample is compared with S-doped samples, an additional absorbance peaks around 1120 cm⁻¹ related to the symmetric stretching vibration of sulfate are noticed¹⁴. In

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of prepared S doped and pure TiO₂ nanoparticles.

detail, the peaks observed at 1120 cm⁻¹ correspond to the physically absorbed SO₂. Moreover, the distinctive peaks of the Ti-O-S bonds are not seen in the undoped TiO₂ sample. The same absorbance peak in the two samples corresponding to the hydroxyl groups and surface adsorbed water molecules O-H bending vibration¹³.

The elemental compositions of the samples are confirmed by the EDS spectroscopy, as given in Fig. 3 and Table 1. The doped sample yields 96 wt.% TiO₂ and 3 wt.% of sulfur whereas undoped samples yield 99 wt.% of TiO₂. The observed results are reveal that sulfur doped in sample. The same kind of results is observed from XRF analysis as shown in Table 1. The FESEM images (Fig. 3) of the samples shows a weakly agglomerated spherical nanoparticles and its size ranges from several tens to hundred nanometres. The TEM images further confirms the spherical morphology as shown

Fig. 3. FESEM image of prepared S doped (a, b) and pure (c, d) TiO₂ nanoparticles with EDS spectra.

Table 1. EDX and XRF analysis of TiO₂ nanoparticles

Prepared samples	EDX analysis		XRF analysis	
	Composition	Mass (%)	Composition	Weight (%)
S-TiO ₂	TiO ₂	96.43	TiO ₂	99
	S	02.87		
Pure-TiO ₂	TiO ₂	99.12	TiO ₂	99

in the FESEM images. The selected area diffraction (SAED) patterns are indexed as crystalline nature. The observed SAED pattern well matched with the XRD (Fig. 3) pattern.

The band gap energy of TiO₂ nanoparticles were calculated using measured optical absorption spectra values. Fig. 5 gives the diffused scattering UV-Vis spectra for TiO₂ nanoparticles. The band gap energy was calculated according to Max Planck's energy equation (eq. (1)). The onset wavelength (λ) was measured by extrapolating the absorption edge on the energy axis. For S-TiO₂ nanoparticles shows an onset of absorption $\lambda_{OS} = 390$ nm, where as pure TiO₂ nanoparticles $\lambda_{OS} = 418$ nm. Meanwhile the band gap val-

Fig. 4. TEM image of prepared S doped (a) and pure (b) TiO₂ nanoparticles with SAED.

Fig. 5. UV-Visible spectra of prepared S doped and pure TiO₂ nanoparticles.

ues 3.17 eV and 2.96 eV respectively for doped and pure samples (Table 2). The nature of the band gap either an indirect or direct transition was established by following power expression for the variation of the absorption coefficient (α) with energy was examined and determined from the eq. (1).

$$\alpha = (2.303 \times 10^3)(A)/l \quad (1)$$

where A is measured absorption and l is the optical path length (l) (1 cm).

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = K_i(h\nu - E_g) \quad (2)$$

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2} = K_d(h\nu - E_g) \quad (3)$$

where, K_i and K_d is the absorption constant for an indirect and direct transitions, $h\nu$ is absorption energy and E_g is the band gap energy.

Table 2. Band gap energy of the as-prepared TiO₂ nanoparticles

Prepared samples	Band gap energy, E_g (eV) Calculation method		
	Max Planck's energy	Indirect transition	Direct transition
S-TiO ₂	2.96	2.90	3.02
Pure-TiO ₂	3.17	3.05	3.21

Fig. 6. Plot of $\alpha^{1/2}$ versus E_{phot} for indirect transition.

The absorption data were fitted to indirect band gap transition eq. (2) and direct band gap transition eq. (3). The Fig. 8 shows the $\alpha^{1/2}$ versus E_{phot} plot for an indirect transition and Fig. 7 shows the $(\alpha E_{phot})^2$ versus E_{phot} for a direct transition. In this absorption coefficient (α) is calculated using eq. (1) and E_{phot} is calculated. In Fig. 8 the value of E_{phot}

extrapolated to $\alpha = 0$ gives an absorption energy, which corresponds to a band gap E_g . The indirect fit plot yield band gap values of 2.90 eV and 3.05 eV respectively for S-TiO₂ and pure TiO₂ nanoparticles. The result in values of E_g estimated from the Fig. 7, the $\alpha = 0$ extrapolation as in the direct band gap values are 3.02 eV for S-TiO₂ and 3.21 eV for pure TiO₂ nanoparticles.

Fig. 7. Plot of $(\alpha E_{\text{phot}})^2$ versus E_{phot} for direct transition.

As tabulated in Table 2, it is interfered that the direct transitions plots are more appropriate than the indirect one when compared to the bandgap value determined using Max Plank energy equation. There is a shift in absorption peak from UV to visible when it is from pure to doped TiO₂ nanoparticles. It is occur due to transfer of charge from the valence band to conduction band. The lower band gap energy (2.96–3.0 eV) is obtained for S-TiO₂ samples when compared to pure-TiO₂ samples band gap energy (3.17–3.2 eV).

Fig. 8. PL emission spectra of prepared S doped and pure TiO₂ nanoparticles.

Fig. 8 shows PL spectra with similar curve shape and the position of the luminescence bands are associated to the crystalline structure and oxygen vacancies of the samples. A slight blue shift in the band intensity of the samples S-TiO₂ samples with respect to undoped TiO₂ sample¹⁵, it is seen due to the influence of the sulfur ions. The result confirms that the existence of oxygen vacancies in the sample is provided due to the decrease in the intensity of the band and excitation wavelength. Oxygen vacancies are created owing to the non-metal doped (sulfur) in the samples¹⁶.

Conclusions

A simple approach was employed to prepare S-TiO₂ nanoparticles via a one step sol-gel process. The prepared particles was characterised using XRD, FTIR, SEM with EDS, TEM, UV-Vis and PL analysis. The S-TiO₂ particles show the more absorption in UV as well in visible region when compared to pure TiO₂. The enhancement in the UV-Vis region was mainly attributed to the sulfur dopant, which enhanced the visible light adsorption as a result of their light harvesting property in the visible range due to the surface Plasmon effect. In addition, the presence of the sulfur dopant helps to reduce the band gap and shift the optical absorbance toward the visible region. The S-TiO₂ nanoparticles have continued to be highly active photocatalytic and photovoltaic applications.

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